

Thermochemistry of Copper(II)-Glycinate in tert-Butanol-Water and Glycerol-Water Mixtures at 25°

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The enthalpies of formation of the Cu(II)-glycinate in water and mixed solvents such as tert-butanol-water and glycerol-water media at 25° have been determined by calorimetry. The entropy-change and the free energy change in water have been calculated using the values of stability constant from literature. Results have been interpreted in terms of "structure-breaking" and "structure-making" effect. The role of solvents on the thermodynamic parameters has been discussed.

AMINO acids form complexes with metal ions in solution. They are of great importance in biochemical processes, since they have been used as model compounds for understanding the thermodynamic behaviour of proteins. Nozaki and Tanford¹ measured the solubilities of several amino acids in water and other solvents in order to evaluate the standard free energy contributions of non-polar groups of the conformational stability of proteins. Question arises concerning the detailed structure and reactions of ribonucleic acid, deoxyribonucleic acid, and their constituent base, sugar and phosphate units. Answering of these questions requires a knowledge of the sites and thermodynamic quantities associated with the interaction of protons and metal ions with these substances.

Co-ordination of an amino acid $H_2N(CH_2)_xCOOH$ takes place through the amino nitrogen and the carboxylic group (generally as the carboxylate ion) according to the following reaction :

Various thermodynamic data are available for the formation of transition metal complexes of amino acids in aqueous medium. Thornton and Skinner² determined the enthalpies of reactions of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) with glycine, serine, threonine and histidine in water. Stack and Skinner³ determined the heats of formation of chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Zn(II) with glycine in water. Gergely, Nagypal and Sovago⁴ have determined the thermodynamics of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) with glycine and of Cu(II) with serine and threonine in aqueous medium. The complexes of amino acids with transition metals have been studied by various methods⁵⁻¹¹, "Calorimetry", "Potentiometry", "pH-metry" and "temperature coefficient methods". Although studies on the complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and especially Cu(II) in aqueous medium have received much attention, knowledge of the thermodynamic data in mixed solvents are still lacking. Such studies will throw light on the solvent

effects—solute-solvent, solvent-solvent interactions on the thermodynamic parameters.

In this communication we report the thermodynamic parameters of Cu(II)-glycinate in water at 25°, and the enthalpy of formation of Cu(II)-glycinate in tert-butanol-water and glycerol-water media at 25°.

Experimental

Glycerol and tert-butanol were purified by methods described in an earlier communication^{1,2}. Copper sulphate solution was prepared by weighing directly $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (B.D.H.—A.R.) and dissolving in a known quantity of $HClO_4$. The purity was checked by estimating the copper content by iodometry. The solution was used within several hours. Glycine (E. Merck-G.R.) was dried at 110° for one hour. It was then dissolved in a calculated quantity of NaOH solution to form sodium glycinate. The reacting solutions were taken in the same mixed solvent.

Perchloric acid and caustic soda were of analar grade and estimated in the usual way. All solutions were made with double-distilled water from an all-glass distilling set.

The details of the calorimeter used have been reported earlier^{1,2}. Some modifications have been made, the bridge now being energized by a stabilized power supply. For calibration also a stabilized power source is used.

For the measurement of the enthalpy change of Cu(II)-glycinate in water, 5 ml of freshly prepared $CuSO_4$ solution (concentration ranging between 0.2-0.25M) in $HClO_4$ was taken in a glass bulb and 250 ml of large excess of glycine (concentration ~0.15M) in NaOH was taken in the Dewar flask. Both were taken in aqueous medium.

For the measurement of enthalpy change of formation of Cu(II)-glycinate in glycerol-water medium, concentration of CuSO_4 were taken between $(2.6-4.3) \times 10^{-2} M$ and concentration of glycine was taken $\sim 2 \times 10^{-2} M$, whereas in tert-butanol-water medium concentrations of CuSO_4 were taken between $(1.3-1.85) \times 10^{-2} M$ and that of glycine $\sim 1 \times 10^{-2} M$. Both solutions were prepared in the same mixed solvent. Calculated amount of NaOH solution of known strength was taken so as to maintain the final pH of the solution between 9.7-12. Concentration of glycine was always more than ten times the concentration of Cu^{++} ion.

Results

Since a small amount of Cu^{++} is reacted with large excess of glycine in the pH range 9.7-12, we get the enthalpy change for 1 : 2 type of complex². Two reactions occur simultaneously,

(where HA stands for glycine)

From the total heat liberated (Q_1), we can get ΔH for reaction (1) after correction for liberation of heat, (Q_2), due to reaction (2) using the relation

$$\Delta H = -\frac{Q}{x}$$

where $Q (=Q_1 - Q_2)$ is the liberated heat in calories for x moles of CuA_2 formed.

We have used fairly dilute solutions, $[\text{Cu}^{++}] \approx 10^{-3} M$ and all the Cu^{++} ions is complexed in the reaction. For different concentration of Cu^{++} ion and over a range of pH 9.85-12 of the solution after reaction we note that ΔH is the same within experimental error. So we have taken the experimental ΔH as ΔH° . The stability constant of Cu-glycinate has been determined by Gergely and coworkers⁴. Using this value, ΔG° and ΔS° in water at 25° are calculated from the relations :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T}$$

Results are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

The values of the stability constants in tert-butanol-water and glycerol-water media are not available in literature. So ΔG° and ΔS° in the mixed solvents could not be calculated.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR $\text{Cu}^{++} + 2\text{A}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}_2$ IN WATER AT 25°C

No. of obs.	Concentration of Cu^{++} (M) $\times 10$	Heat liberated in Joules	Enthalpy change $-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	Average $-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹
1		68.54	54.43			
2	2.5180	68.80	54.64			
3		68.71	54.56			
4		60.74	54.48			
5	2.2300	60.93	54.64	54.52 \pm 0.12	85.90	105.23
6		60.93	54.64			
7		54.27	54.27			
8	2.0000	54.48	54.48			
9		54.56	54.56			

Volume of Cu^{++} soln. taken for reaction = 5 ml.

TABLE 2—ENTHALPY CHANGE FOR $\text{Cu}^{++} + 2\text{A}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}_2$ IN TERT-BUTANOL-WATER AND GLYCEROL-WATER MEDIA AT 25°C

Wt. % of tert-butanol or glycerol	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹ in t-butanol-water	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹ in glycerol-water
10	56.65 \pm 0.33	59.50 \pm 0.08
20	59.12 \pm 0.29	62.89 \pm 0.08
30	62.80 \pm 0.38	61.63 \pm 0.17
40	61.34 \pm 0.29	60.71 \pm 0.21
50	60.17 \pm 0.21	59.91 \pm 0.17

Discussion

A number of workers have determined the enthalpy of formation of Cu(II)-glycinate in aqueous medium at 25°. The results are given below :

ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	Method
-54.39	Cal. ⁴
-55.15	Cal. ^{1,4}
-51.88	Cal. ^{1,5}
-53.56*	Cal. ³
-48.53 \pm 2.09	Equil. ¹¹
-54.52 \pm 0.12	Cal. (our value)

(Cal. = calorimetric,

Equil. = temperature dependence of equilibrium constants,

* measured at 20.5°.

Our value is in good agreement with that reported by Gergely and coworkers⁴. Other values differ slightly from our value probably due to the not well-chosen experimental conditions as observed by Gergely *et al*⁴.

Figures 1 and 2 represent the plots of $-\Delta H^\circ$ (K cal/mole) against weight percent, mole fraction of organic constituent of the solvent and reciprocal

Fig. 1. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$ against solvent composition.

Fig. 2. Plot of $-\Delta H^\circ$ against $\frac{1}{D}$.

of dielectric constant of aqueo-organic solvent. The dielectric constant values necessary are taken from Conway¹⁶ and Akerlof¹⁷.

As may be seen from the diagram, the heat of formation ($-\Delta H^\circ$) passes through a maximum around 30 wt % of tert-butanol in tert-butanol-water system and 20 wt % of glycerol in glycerol-water medium. These findings may be explained in the light of the interpretation of the behaviour of glycine in water and in ethanol-water media by earlier workers¹⁸⁻²¹.

Amino acids are highly polar. They contain differing non-polar side chains. Longsworth¹⁸ has studied the diffusion of amino acids in water and has concluded that glycine is a "structure-breaker" in water. Kay and Evans¹⁹ has drawn similar conclusions from the interpretation of the temperature dependence of the walden products of the amino acids in aqueous solution. In addition, Robinson²⁰ has interpreted the behaviour of the partial molal entropy of water in aqueous solution of the amino acids that glycine is a net "structure-breaker" while the higher aliphatic homologues are "structure makers". Spink and Auker²¹ studied the heat of solution of amino acids in water and water-ethanol medium. The positive transfer entropies support the interpretation that glycine is even more effective as a "structure-breaker" in alcohol-water medium than in water, at least up to 0.1 mole fraction of ethanol. The increased "structure-breaking" by glycine in the mixed solvent is likely due to the already enhanced structure in the original solvent mixtures. Thus the unfavourable free-energy of transfer of glycine from water to aqueous ethanol mixtures is a result of "structure-breaking" effect that causes the entropy and enthalpy terms to be positive with the enthalpy contribution dominating. From the present results, glycine appears to be more effective "structure-breaker" in tert-butanol-water and glycerol-water media similar to the observation already reported²¹. The maximum structuration corresponds to maximum enthalpy of transfer.

The maximum structuration of tert-butanol-water mixtures at about 30 wt % also agrees with the observation of Pointud, Morel and Juillard²², in their study of the behaviour of LiCl in tert-butanol-water medium, both enthalpies and entropies of transfer show maxima at 0.08 mole fraction of tert-butanol (27 wt %).

This maximum structuration model is also supported by some thermodynamic and spectroscopic arguments²³⁻²⁵.

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